

Quantum Elastic Scattering from a Spherical Infinite Potential and Directional Probability Equilibrium

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In a previous note, we asked the question: How does a single photon approaching an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction in a one-dimensional problem know what its probability to reflect or refract is? We argued that this probability does not follow from some stochastic feature of the junction, but rather from a directional probability $\exp(ipx)$. We argued that $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability linked with conservation of momentum in Newtonian scattering and implies that there is a spatial uncertainty region of \hbar/p . We argued that within a Δx region of the n_1 - n_2 junction, the photon is able to establish a “balance” or equilibrium of the incident, reflected and refracted photon, because one does not know which it is during the time spent in Δx . We argued that one must describe this by a balance of $A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip_2x)$ at $x=0$ and a similar equation obtained taking d/dx . It is this balance or equilibrium which determines the weights of B and C relative to A, i.e. essentially solves the problem.

If this is in fact the process which occurs, then we argue here that it should also apply to the scattering of a particle from a spherical infinite well potential at r_0 , for example. In other words, we consider all of the possible directional probability solutions outside of r_0 together as these participate in the balance or equilibrium at r_0 , the interaction region. In such a case, one has a general solution of the Schrodinger equation of: $A_l j_l(pr) + B_l n_l(pr)$ ((1)), where j_l is a Bessel function, and n_l , a Neumann. In order to have equilibrium between all possible $\exp(ipx)$ type directional probabilities, one must establish a constraint condition just as in the n_1 - n_2 problem. The constraint condition for the infinite spherical potential at r_0 is that there is no probability for r_0 inside.

Thus, we argue that the relevant weights in the problem (i.e. the solution of the problem) are established by the constraint condition at the interaction surface. This leads to $0 = A_l j_l(pr_0) + B_l n_l(pr_0)$ ((2)). This yields a relative weight between A_l and B_l . The question is then: How does this relate to anything physical? The fact is that even though ((1)) is a general math solution, with B_l now given in terms of A_l through ((2)), one may now rewrite ((1)) in terms of a math sum of physical directional probabilities, namely $\exp(ipz)$ (incident particle) and $f(\theta) \exp(ipr)/r$ (scattered particle).

Thus, it is the use of directional probabilities (linked to momentum conservation) and constraint conditions which govern the weights of the allowable directional probabilities at an interaction point/region, i.e. r_0 in the spherical infinite potential case and $x=0$ in the n_1 - n_2 junction reflection-refraction case. In particular, if one has an incident particle linked with $\exp(ipz)$ one wishes to know the weight $f(\theta)$ of $\exp(ipr)/r$ in order to find out what per cent of particles scatter into angle θ . This means finding a relative weight between the two directional probabilities and this occurs by a probabilistic sampling of all solutions at the interaction point (here r_0). Then, only one choice of outcome occurs, but in keeping with the probabilistic balance, just as in the n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction reflection-refraction situation.

We then try to generalize to the one-dimensional quantum bound state situation.

Directional Probability

Ultimately, as in Newtonian mechanics, one considers problems which involve a particle interacting in some manner, be it with a 2-slit apparatus (etc), an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction or a potential $V(x)$. In Newtonian mechanics, such interactions are deterministic with the particle being a point which is acted upon by a force.

In previous notes, however, we suggested that one may introduce a probability directly into Newtonian 2-body elastic scattering. In particular, for an incident (e_1, e_2) energy and (p_1, p_2) momentum vectors, any outcome (e_i, e_j) , (p_i, p_j) which conserves energy and momentum has equal product probability. This then is an interacting scenario with a probability. We argued that such a probability should be a complex number with unit modulus as there is no real value weight for a free particle. We noted that there are many problems with using $\exp(iE C_1)$ and $\exp(i p C_2)$, but that introducing Lorentz invariance of the probability and time reversal invariance ($p \rightarrow -p$, $x \rightarrow -x$) for $\exp(ipx)$ leads to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. Such a formalism suggests a characteristic uncertainty in x , called the wavelength \hbar/p and gives rise to the non-Newtonian interaction with a 2-slit apparatus. The $\exp(ipx)$ form also has consequences on other interactions, we argue.

Interaction Time in a Time-Independent Interaction Problem

Given $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, one may note that due to the uncertainty in t and x given by this probability, one is not following a particle in terms of $x(t)$ as in Newtonian mechanics. In fact, $\exp(-iEt)$ may be used separately to analyze time uncertainty and $\exp(ipx)$, spatial uncertainty. In a 2-slit calculation one may use $\exp(ipx)$ s alone and this may be extended to reflection/refraction at an n_1 - n_2 junction and from a potential $V(r)$.

There is a big issue, however, with using $\exp(ipx)$ s as probabilities which add and by ignoring time. It means that one may add $\exp(ipx)$ s representing very different times. For example, in an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction reflection-refraction problem, one writes:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) \quad (\text{i.e. incident and reflected photon}) \quad ((1a))$$

and in an elastic scattering problem, one writes:

$$\exp(ipz) + f(\theta) \exp(ipr)/r \quad ((1b)) \quad \text{incident and scattered particles}$$

An incident and a reflected particle exist at different times and even though probabilities add in OR situations, the physical situations do not coexist at the same time. One might argue that there is a steady state picture, but the same result must hold for a single particle and in that case, the times are different. We argue, however, that there is a very important "catch", namely the interaction time.

The key is to solve an interaction problem. This essentially means finding B in terms of A in ((1a)) and the weight $f(\theta)$ in ((1b)) given a weight of 1 for $\exp(ipz)$. There is a classical time-related probability in the problems ((1a)) ((1b)) which differs from the directional probability “ $\exp(ipx)$ ”. It is the $\exp(ipx)$ directional probability which may be used to find the classical probability in time in the following manner we argue. At an interaction point (math), there is x uncertainty due to $\exp(ipx)$ (and time uncertainty due to $\exp(-iEt)$ which we do not consider). We have argued in previous notes that this means that for reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction, one may have either the incident, reflected or refracted particle in a tiny dx region as the interaction occurs. One may write a kind of probability balance or equilibrium based on some continuity equation(s) at this interaction point, we argue. In the n_1 - n_2 problem one has:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((2a))$$

$$A p \exp(ipx) - pB \exp(-ipx) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2s) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((2b))$$

It is these two continuity equations which define a kind of directional probability equilibrium during the interaction, we argue, and allow one to find B and C in terms of A, which is the goal of the problem.

We argue that for an interaction with a potential, there must be a similar continuity or balance equation for the various $\exp(ipx)$ s involved at the interaction point or region. This is the approach to solving the probabilistic problem, we argue.

Interaction with an Infinite Spherical Potential

We consider a particle being sent along the z axis which interacts with a hard sphere, i.e. an infinite spherical potential with radius r_0 . The particle may pass through if it is above the sphere, or interact. The question is: What percentage of the particles interact and scatter into an angle θ ?

In order to solve this problem, one may suggest that there should be an equation allowing for a kind of balance/equilibrium between $\exp(ipz)$ and the scattered particle, described by:

$$f(\theta) \exp(ipr)/r \quad ((3))$$

The question is then to find this equation. We first note that in principle in an elastic problem, one may consider an energy balance equation:

$$\text{Kinetic energy} + V(r) = \text{Energy} \quad ((4))$$

Here, one uses kinetic energy = $1/2m (-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad})$ because one deals with $\exp(ipx)$ directional probabilities. Outside $r=r_0$, the potential is 0 and so one must find the most general solution of Kinetic energy = E. The math solution is:

$A_l j_l(kr) + B_l n_l(kr)$ for $r > r_0$ ((5)) where j_l is a Bessel function and n_l , a Neumann

A_l and B_l are completely unknown and so one seeks to find B_l in terms of A_l .

Above, we argued that physically one should have the directional derivatives $\exp(ipz)$ and $f(\theta)\exp(ipr)/r$. One should be able to write ((5)) in terms of these two probabilities, but first may use ((5)) to find a relation between A_l and B_l at the interaction region, i.e. at

$$r=r_0 \quad ((6))$$

At this point, ((5)) must vanish because for an infinite well potential, there can be no probability inside $r < r_0$. Thus:

$$0 = A_l j_l(kr_0) + B_l n_l(kr_0) \quad ((7))$$

((7)) provides a relation between A_l and B_l which is the key to solving the problem. A constraint/boundary condition (balance equation between the two particle directional probabilities at the interaction region) solves the problem. All that is left is to show how A_l and B_l are linked with $\exp(ipz)$ and $f(\theta)\exp(ipr)/r$.

To do so, we consider $r \rightarrow \infty$, but note that the problem has been essentially solved at the interaction region $r=r_0$. Considerations of the $r \rightarrow \infty$ limit only lead to an association of A_l , B_l with $\exp(ipz)$ and $f(\theta)\exp(ipr)/r$ and $f(\theta)$ is linked to how many particles scatter into angle θ . (We use k and p interchangeably.)

The analysis we use follows (1). For $r \rightarrow \infty$:

$$j_l(kr) \rightarrow \sin(kr - l\pi/2) / (kr) \quad \text{and} \quad n_l(kr) \rightarrow -\cos(kr - l\pi/2) / (kr) \quad ((8))$$

and

$$\exp(ikz) = \sum_l \frac{1}{(2ik)^l} \sum_{i=0}^{2l+1} \{ \exp(ikr - l\pi/2) - \exp(-i(kr - l\pi/2)) \} P_l(\cos(\theta)) \quad ((9))$$

Here $P_l(\cos(\theta))$ is the Legendre polynomial.

((8)) may be linked directly to $\exp(ikz)$ and the remaining pieces must be $f(\theta)\exp(ipr)/r$.

In particular, (from (1)) for the hard-sphere case:

$$((5)) \text{ for } r \rightarrow \infty = \frac{1}{kr} (A_l \sin(kr - l\pi/2) - B_l \cos(kr - l\pi/2))$$

$$= \frac{1}{kr} \sqrt{A_l^2 + B_l^2} \sin(kr - l\pi/2 + \delta(l)) \quad ((10)) \quad (\text{from (1)})$$

where $\delta(l) = \arctan(-B_l/A_l)$ which is known using ((7))

Now using ((8)) and ((9)), (1) shows that in general:

$$((5)) \text{ at } r \rightarrow \text{infinite} = \exp(ikz + \text{Sum over } l (2l+1) (\exp(2i \text{delta}(l)-1)/(2ik) P_l(\cos(\theta))) \exp(ikr)/r$$

Thus, $f(\theta)$ is known if one knows $\text{delta}(l)$ which is precisely what ((7)) gives.

As a result, the elastic scattering problem is essentially solved by considering a balance/equilibrium equation at the interaction region, i.e. ((7)). This we argue is the essential physics linked with using the directional probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ s.

Bound Quantum State

We now try to generalize to the one-dimensional bound quantum state. In such a case, we know that a particle interacts at each x with a $V(x)$. At any x , a given p may be described by $\exp(ipx)$ and if $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$, p may be given any impulse hit k . One should consider $\exp(ipx)$ and all other possible outcomes at x , namely all $\exp(ipx)$. The question is: What is the balance/equilibrium equation at x ? We suggest that it is conservation of energy, i.e.

$$\{\text{Sum over } p a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx) \} / \{\text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)\} + V(x) = E \quad ((11))$$

There is then a second boundary condition which exists at $x \rightarrow \text{infinite}$ and $x \rightarrow -\text{infinite}$ namely that:

$$\text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) \text{ tends to } 0 \quad ((12))$$

Again the directional probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ and some kind of balance or constraint equation at an interaction point x leads to ((11)) and a second constraint to a solution at $x \rightarrow \pm \text{infinite}$ at which the interaction has stopped. We argue that this is consistent with the arguments made above.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that there exists a directional probability in Newtonian 2-body scattering, namely $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. This probability suggests an uncertainty in x involved in interactions involving p as seen experimentally in the interaction of a particle with both slits of a 2-slit apparatus, if the slits are separated by about \hbar/p . The goal in many physical problems is to describe a probabilistic feature of an interaction. In a reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction, the goal is to find the probability to reflect and refract. These are not directional probabilities, but are governed by them, we argue. In the case of scattering from a potential $V(r)$, one has $\exp(ipz) + f(\theta) \exp(ipr)/r$ and wants to know $f(\theta)$ which is associated with the probability to scatter into an angle θ . Thus, there is probability not only in Newtonian 2-body scattering, but in other interaction problems as well. The key idea is that it is

the directional probability form “ $\exp(ipx)$ ” which solves these problems. The question is then: How is this done?

In previous notes, we argued that for reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 junction at $x=0$, there is actually uncertainty in position at $x=0$ due to $\exp(ipx)$. We thus suggested that a directional probability equilibrium or balance occurs in this dx because one does not know if one has an incident, reflected or refracted particle in dx . This is equivalent to two continuity equations at $x=0$, namely:

$$A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \text{ and } A\exp(ipx) - pB\exp(-ipx) = Cp_2\exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0$$

This, in turn, yields B and C in terms of A, which is essentially the solution of the problem.

We argue here that this same idea applies to scattering from a potential $V(r)$ and consider the case of a hard sphere, i.e. an infinite potential at $r=r_0$. The idea is that one considers a balance/equilibrium of directional probabilities at the interaction region again, which is $r=r_0$. In principle, the physical directional probabilities are $\exp(ipz)$ and $f(\theta)\exp(ipr)/r$. Mathematically, however, one may solve: $-1/2m \text{ grad dot grad Function} = E \text{ function}$. This leads to an r -dependence in a general solution of $A_l j_l(kr) + B_l n_l(kr)$. This solution must be 0 at $r=r_0$. It is this equation (the balance of the directional probabilities at the interaction) which essentially solves the problem. One then may consider $r \rightarrow \text{infinite}$ so that one may compare the form: $\exp(ikz) + f(\theta)\exp(ikr)/r$ with $\{A_l j_l(kr) + B_l n_l(kr)\} g(l) P_l(\cos(\theta))$ where $g(l)$ is a known function in l . This leads one to find $f(\theta)$ which is directly linked to the probability to scatter in a direction θ . The problem, however, is essentially solved at the interaction point using a balance of directional probabilities there. We then extend these ideas to one-dimensional bound states.

References

1. Shankar, R. Principles of Quantum Mechanics (Plenum, 1988)